

Supplementary Appendix II– Extended Materials

This supplementary appendix is linked to the article entitled “The potential of the Blue Economy to promote the generation of sustainable employment in the European Union.” It contains valuable content that could not be accommodated within the journal’s word limit and is made available here for transparency and scholarly completeness. In particular, the document expands upon the Literature review, Results, Discussions and Conclusions that were necessarily abbreviated in the main submission.

Literature Review

Similarly, for several years to date many sources have denounced that oceans are turning into a global swamp due to plastic pollution (Abbing, 2019) . To aggravate the dimensions of this ecological catastrophe, other sources such as GIZ (2021) confirm that the generalized rise in ocean levels as a consequence of climate change associated with the degradation of the planet (Daly et al., 2021; Kuwae et al., 2022; Shiiba et al., 2022; Tanaka et al., 2022), will inevitably entail the disappearance of several nations in the Pacific Ocean, the so-called SIDS (Small Island Developing States) (Cheng et al., 2021; Hassanali, 2020; Louey, 2022; Mallin, 2018). In response to this disheartening scenario, the Blue Economy enacts the defense of the oceanic biodiversity (Tanaka et al., 2022; Vierros & Harden-Davies, 2020) through the development of *ad hoc* programs towards the conservation of marine wildlife. Several of these programs have been centered on the protection of invertebrates that compose and inhabit the coral reefs, particularly the subphylum *anthozoa* (Obura, 2020; Phelan et al., 2020), since the social and economic development of the countries of the Pacific Basin depends on these ecosystems, if not their very existence (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2017).

Results

In an intermediate range of from 920,000 to 550,000 workers fall the sea façades corresponding to the Adriatic-Ionian Sea, the Baltic Sea, and the North Sea, with the latter two areas showing the least variability over the analyzed period (2009-2017). Finally, we conclude that the two ocean basins in which less blue jobs are generated in absolute terms are located in the easternmost part of the European Union: the East Mediterranean and the Black Sea, within

a range that fluctuates between 100,000 and 500,000 workers. Consequently, it is confirmed that the ocean basins that exhibit a higher degree of variability (e.g. Mediterranean and Adriatic-Ionian Sea) are those in which variables Coastal Tourism (*CT*), Living Resources (*LR*), and Port Activities (*PA*) have a higher presence.

Discussion

This research, aimed at analyzing the impact of the Blue Economy on job creation across the European Union, firstly demonstrates that the Blue Economy has transcended for many years now the Ocean Economy as defined by Colgan (2003), i.e., having repercussions only and solely in countries with a maritime coastline. On the contrary, the Blue Economy also has a remarkable presence in the landlocked countries of the European Union (Austria, Czechia, Hungary, Luxembourg, and Slovakia), although its importance is eminently less than in the rest of the countries analyzed. From a fixed-effects panel data regression performed on the 27 member states of the European Union over the period 2009-2018, based on data obtained from The EU Blue Economy Report (European Commission, 2021), it can be noted that our findings are also confirmed by the prevailing literature. For instance, the high statistical significance of the variable *LR* (Living Resources) (given a *p*-value less than 0.001), denotes the huge specific weight of the EU fishing industries and aquaculture sector at a global level (Guillen et al., 2019). However, the negative sign of the regression can be explained by the drastic effects of climate change (Hoerterer et al., 2020), which have considerably reduced the capture of certain fish species (ie. sardine, mackerel, or bluefin tuna) (Peck et al., 2020) or the decline in the usual production of the European fish farms (Maulu et al., 2021; Peck et al., 2020).

In the same vein, the set of Common Fisheries Policies (CFPs) enacted by the European Union (Daw & Gray, 2005), in particular, the system of quotas granted to the different member states for fishing in certain seas or for capturing certain endemic species, has also influenced in the lower contribution to the Blue Economy of this variable. In fact, the coastal populations themselves have been made aware of the gravity of depleting fish resources or the elevated marine pollution (Garza-Gil et al., 2021), in a context of uncertainty denominated the “Blue degrowth” (Hadjimichael, 2018). With identical statistical significance, but in a positive sense, the variable *CT* (Coastal Tourism) represents the main pole of growth of jobs generated by the Blue Economy. The rise of sustainable tourism (Brumbaugh & Patil, 2017) caused by the Rio +20 or the Earth Summit conference (Kabil et al., 2021), has resulted in novel and sustainable initiatives such as the fact of integrating on an environmentally friendly way, tourism practices

with fishing (Hall, 2021). In the case of blue jobs generated from the exploitation of non-renewable resources coming from the seas, their positive impact on the Blue Economy has been due to an exhaustive knowledge of the functioning of underwater ecosystems (Glover et al., 2018), a scheme that has enabled the extraction of minerals, oil, or natural gas (Kaczynski, 2012), with minimal damage to marine fauna and flora. Note that such a degree of development of non-renewable resources associated with the Blue Economy would not have been possible without the prior consideration of a number of rather complex factors (historical, economic, legal, environmental, etc.) (Charlier & Charlier, 1992).

Finally, it can be observed that, in the light of this research, the only variable that lacks statistical significance is *OE* (Ocean Energy), which is probably the great unresolved issue of the European Blue Economy, given its negligible contribution to the creation of European blue jobs. In any case, this problem, which is crucial for the advancement of a truly self-sustainable blue economy, is not strictly European but global. In this sense, IRENA (2020) points out that the expansion of offshore energies is still limited by purely technological and geographical factors.

Conclusions

In our view, this work may give rise to new lines of research. For example, replicating the analysis carried out using variables even more representative of the Blue Economy of the present, such as those defined by Lagemann (2021), i.e., Blue Bioeconomy, Coastal and environmental protection, Defence and security, Desalination, Marine minerals/Deep-seabed mining, Marine research, and Education. It could also be interesting to analyze the impact of the Blue Economy on the basis of ocean facades rather than countries, although European countries without an ocean coastline would not be taken into account. At an inter-company level, it would be worthwhile to examine the overall performance of companies on the basis of the Blueness Index, a measure recently established by Mumtaz & Smith (2022), which acts as a benchmark for investors who are firmly committed to the environmental and socio-economic benefits of the Blue Economy.

To conclude, it should be emphasized several practical policies that could be implemented on the basis of this research. Among them, it should be emphasized that Marine Spatial Planning should be elaborated taking into account the real needs of all stakeholders involved in the Blue Economy and not just some of them. Such is the case of port activities and maritime transport

in which huge public and private investments are concerned, and which are not always presented *de facto* as respectful of the fundamental schemes of the Blue Economy. Inevitably, public authorities must take into account the innovation and use of new technologies as the only feasible alternative for the generation of sustainable offshore energy. They should also take into account the need to raise public awareness of the benefits of the Blue Economy (Raimi & Kah, 2022) or that the Blue Economy itself represents a unique opportunity to advance toward gender equality in the workplace (Bertarelli, 2021).

References

- Abbing, M. R. (2019). *Plastic Soup: An Atlas of Ocean Pollution*. Washington, D.C.: Island Press.
- Bertarelli, D. (2021). *The blue economy is an ocean of opportunity to advance gender equality*. unctad.org/news/blue-economy-ocean-opportunity-advance-gender-equality, accessed 29 September 2022
- Brumbaugh, R., & Patil, P. (2017). *Sustainable tourism can drive the blue economy: Investing in ocean health is synonymous with generating ocean wealth*. blogs.worldbank.org/voices/Sustainable-Tourism-Can-Drive-the-Blue-Economy, accessed 29 September 2022
- Charlier, R. H., & Charlier, C. C. (1992). Ocean non-living resources: historical perspective on exploitation, economics and environmental impact. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 40(2–3), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207239208710721>
- Cheng, Y.-T., Tseng, Y.-C., Iwaki, Y., & Huang, M. C. (2021). Sustainable food security in Small Island Developing States (SIDS): A case of Horticulture project in Marshall Islands. *Marine Policy*, 128, 104378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104378>
- Colgan, C. S. (2003). *Measurement of the Ocean and Coastal Economy: Theory and Methods*. cbe.miis.edu/noep_publications/3, accessed 29 September 2022
- Daly, J., Knott, C., Keogh, P., & Singh, G. G. (2021). Changing climates in a blue economy: Assessing the climate-responsiveness of Canadian fisheries and oceans policy. *Marine Policy*, 131, 104623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104623>
- Daw, T., & Gray, T. (2005). Fisheries science and sustainability in international policy: a study of failure in the European Union's Common Fisheries Policy. *Marine Policy*, 29(3), 189–197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2004.03.003>
- European Commission. (2021). *The EU Blue Economy Report*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2771/8217>
- Garza-Gil, M. ^a. D., Varela-Lafuente, M. M., & Pérez-Pérez, M. I. (2021). The blue economy in the european union: Valuation of spanish small-scale fishers' perceptions on

- environmental and socioeconomic effects. *Panoeconomicus*, 68(4), 461–481.
<https://doi.org/10.2298/PAN180425013G>
- GIZ. (2021). *Coping with climate change in the Pacific island region*.
www.giz.de/en/worldwide/14200.html, accessed 29 September 2022
- Glover, A. G., Wiklund, H., Chen, C., & Dahlgren, T. G. (2018). Managing a sustainable deep-sea ‘blue economy’ requires knowledge of what actually lives there. *ELife*, 7, e41319. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.41319>
- Guillen, J., Asche, F., Carvalho, N., Fernández Polanco, J. M., Llorente, I., Nielsen, R., Nielsen, M., & Villasante, S. (2019). Aquaculture subsidies in the European Union: Evolution, impact and future potential for growth. *Marine Policy*, 104, 19–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.02.045>
- Hadjimichael, M. (2018). A call for a blue degrowth: Unravelling the European Union’s fisheries and maritime policies. *Marine Policy*, 94, 158–164.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.05.007>
- Hall, C. M. (2021). Tourism and fishing. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 21(4), 361–373. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15022250.2021.1955739>
- Hassanali, K. (2020). CARICOM and the blue economy – Multiple understandings and their implications for global engagement. *Marine Policy*, 120, 104137.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104137>
- Hoegh-Guldberg, O., Poloczanska, E. S., Skirving, W., & Dove, S. (2017). Coral Reef Ecosystems under Climate Change and Ocean Acidification. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00158>
- Hoerterer, C., Schupp, M. F., Benkens, A., Nickiewicz, D., Krause, G., & Buck, B. H. (2020). Stakeholder Perspectives on Opportunities and Challenges in Achieving Sustainable Growth of the Blue Economy in a Changing Climate. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 795.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00795>
- IRENA. (2020). *Fostering a blue economy: Offshore renewable energy*. Abu Dhabi: International Renewable Energy Agency.
- Kabil, M., Priatmoko, S., Magda, R., & Dávid, L. D. (2021). Blue Economy and Coastal Tourism: A Comprehensive Visualization Bibliometric Analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3650. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13073650>
- Kaczynski, W. (2012). The Future of Blue Economy: Lessons for European Union. *Foundations of Management*, 3(1), 21–32. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10238-012-0033-8>
- Kuwae, T., Watanabe, A., Yoshihara, S., Suehiro, F., & Sugimura, Y. (2022). Implementation of blue carbon offset crediting for seagrass meadows, macroalgal beds, and macroalgae farming in Japan. *Marine Policy*, 138, 104996.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.104996>

- Lagemann, A. (2021). Measuring the Blue Economy: Challenges at the regional level. *Baltic 4th Forum MSP*.
- Louey, P. (2022). The Pacific blue economy: An instrument of political maneuver. *Marine Policy*, 135, 104880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104880>
- Mallin, M. F. (2018). From sea-level rise to seabed grabbing: The political economy of climate change in Kiribati. *Marine Policy*, 97, 244–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.04.021>
- Maulu, S., Hasimuna, O. J., Haambiya, L. H., Monde, C., Musuka, C. G., Makorwa, T. H., Munganga, B. P., Phiri, K. J., & Nsekanabo, J. D. (2021). Climate Change Effects on Aquaculture Production: Sustainability Implications, Mitigation, and Adaptations. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 609097. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.609097>
- Mumtaz, M. Z., & Smith, Z. A. (2022). The Blueness Index, Investment Choice, and Portfolio Allocation. In P. Morgan, M. C. J. Huang, M. Voyer, D. Benzaken, & A. Watanabe (Eds.), *Blue Economy and Blue Finance: Toward Sustainable Development and Ocean Governance* (pp. 72–92). Tokyo: ADB Institute (ADBI) - Asian Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.56506/HDLZ1912>
- Obura, D. O. (2020). Getting to 2030 - Scaling effort to ambition through a narrative model of the SDGs. *Marine Policy*, 117, 103973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103973>
- Peck, M. A., Catalán, I. A., Damalas, D., Elliott, M., Ferreira, J. G., Hamon, K. G., Kamermans, P., Kay, S., Kreiß, C. M., Pinnegar, J. K., Saille, S. F., & Taylor, N. G. H. (2020). *Climate change and European Fisheries and Aquaculture: “CERES” Project Synthesis Report* (F. Burke, Ed.). Hamburg: EU Horizon 2020 CERES.
- Phelan, A., Ruhanen, L., & Mair, J. (2020). Ecosystem services approach for community-based ecotourism: towards an equitable and sustainable blue economy. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 28(10), 1665–1685. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1747475>
- Raimi, L., & Kah, J. M. L. (2022). *Implications for Entrepreneurship and Enterprise Development in the Blue Economy*. Hershey: IGI Global.
- Shiiba, N., Wu, H. H., Huang, M. C., & Tanaka, H. (2022). How blue financing can sustain ocean conservation and development: A proposed conceptual framework for blue financing mechanism. *Marine Policy*, 139, 104575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104575>
- Tanaka, K., Zhu, M., Miyaji, K., Kurokawa, T., & Akamatsu, T. (2022). Spatial distribution maps of real-time ocean observation platforms and sensors in Japanese waters. *Marine Policy*, 141, 105102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105102>
- Vierros, M. K., & Harden-Davies, H. (2020). Capacity building and technology transfer for improving governance of marine areas both beyond and within national jurisdiction. *Marine Policy*, 122, 104158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104158>